

OBSERVING THROUGH-THICKNESS DAMAGE TIMELINE IN THICK-SECTION MONOLITHIC COMPOSITES UNDER SOFT IMPACT LOAD

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ABSTRACT

The well-known weight saving capacities of composite materials have led to an increased interest in fiber-reinforced plastics as protective solutions for light armoured vehicles against blast threats. When subjected to such threats, materials undergo dynamic loading resulting in high strain rate levels. The majority of intra-laminar material properties such as stiffnesses and strengths are known to increase under dynamic loading. However, the characterization of interlaminar properties in terms of strength and toughness under dynamic conditions is still an open field in research. This paper presents an experimental setup capable of generating interface delaminations under high speed loading and while observing the damage timeline generated in through the thickness of the specimen in real-time. The use of High-Speed photography and Digital Image Correlation allows the experimentalist to measure the displacement field of the specimen, the through-thickness strain field, the onset and the propagation of delamination. Such measurements can then be coupled with explicit FE simulations to determine inversely the dynamic properties of the interfaces. Finally, the experimental results for 21 mm thick E-Glass woven laminates with a polyester resin are presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Extensive literature exists on the effects of dynamic loading on thin composites. A comprehensive literature study by Langdon et al [1] compiles dozens of studies on the dynamic behaviour under air-blast loads of composite configurations typically found in the naval, aircraft and automotive industries. These studies address low area weight composites under loads that generally stem from accidental load cases. It can be concluded that there is a lack of studies concerning thick section monolithic composites (Area Weight > 30 kg.m⁻²). This gap in the literature can be explained by two main factors: the design load cases and the complexity of testing under high-explosive loads.

Firstly, the studies compiled in [1] focus on material systems designed to fulfil structural requirements, such as manoeuvring loads, and not to be the first line of defence against deliberate blast attacks. Such kind of attacks translate into high explosive charges at close range inducing high incident pressures whereas the existing literature remains focused on lower incident pressures against lower area weight composites.

Secondly, testing specimens under close-range explosive loads is a complex task. Such test scenarios require a secure testing ground and military personnel qualified to handle the explosives, detonators, etc. This poses a logistic problem as well as a difficulty to have a controlled and repeatable atmosphere as such test are often conducted outdoors. What's more, the specimens are often difficult to monitor as the explosion may damage the measuring instruments and the resulting explosion products (fireball, debris, etc.) may obscure the view if filmed. Consequently, all the measurements and observations on the specimens can only be performed post-mortem, rendering the real-time observation of damage onset and propagation impossible. As a result, it can be seen in [1] that researchers use simplified testing methodologies, such as metal foam impactors, shock tubes and low explosive charges, in order to circumvent the abovementioned complexities.

One of the damage modes observed during blast test is a massive delamination pattern throughout the thickness of the plate without visible penetration. The plates remain watertight but, after cutting inspections, they reveal severe delaminations.

This paper describes an experimental setup specifically conceived to test thick monolithic composites under highly dynamic loading aiming at generating delaminations without penetration with a focus on monitoring the timeline of damage in real-time as opposed to the traditional post-mortem only observations. Secondly, it presents the experimental results of a series of 21mm thick ($AW = 44 \text{ kg/m}^2$) specimens made of twill 2:2 woven layer of E-glass fibres with a polyester resin (LPET).

2 METHODS

2.1 Experimental setup

An experimental setup is proposed where a narrow beam is cut from a pristine composite panel and then is subjected to a soft impact load using a High Density PolyEthylene (HDPE) cylindrical impactor. The sequence of events is filmed sidewise with High-Speed (HS) photography coupled with Digital Image Correlation (DIC), see Figure 1. The thickness of the beam is hence entirely exposed to the HS cameras and the timeline of damage events can then be observed and recorded, delamination onset and propagation can be tracked. Global deformation of the backface and through-thickness strain fields are also measured.

Figure 1: Experimental setup sketch

The material properties of HDPE make it ideal for generating a soft impact as the impactor deforms substantially upon impact without shattering, avoiding penetration mechanisms to develop and ensuring that only delaminations are generated in the composite specimen. What's more, HDPE is also affordable, readily available, and easy to machine to provide appropriate shaping of the transferred impulse. Russel *et al* [2] and Karthikeyan *et al* [3] used a similar experimental setup but used aluminium foams instead of HDPE impactors. The main disadvantage of using metal foams is that they disintegrate shortly after impact, generating a cloud of debris that obscures the cameras field of view, rendering the observation of the exact damage onset rather difficult.

2.2 Specimen design

The geometry of the composite beam is designed so that the through-thickness stress waves generated by the soft impact can travel through the entire thickness of the beam back and forth from the impact side to the backface before the longitudinal stress waves reach the free end of the beam. The shape and dimensions of the beam can be shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Beam specimen geometry; $L = 240 \text{ mm}$; $w = 22 \text{ mm}$; $t = 21 \text{ mm}$

The thickness side of the beams is painted white to enhance the contrast for delamination detection and is equipped with tracking dots or markers to allow tracking by photogrammetry. The exposed thickness is then captured by the HS cameras with a frame rate of at least 200.000 fps, i.e. a time resolution of $5 \mu\text{s}$. This time resolution is fine enough to capture the through-thickness propagation of the stress waves that generate the onset of delamination.

3 RESULTS

Twenty specimens were tested with impact velocities, V_0 , ranging from 166 m/s to 309 m/s resulting in an impact energy, K_{e0} , ranging from 200 J to 700 J.

3.1 Damage timeline

Damage Mode 0: No exterior damage is observed for impact energies below 240J. The specimen absorbs the impact resulting in a rigid body movement forward in the direction of the impact combined with a free beam vibration response, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Beam response sequence when no damage occurs (Damage Mode 0), $K_{e0} = 214 \text{ J}$.

Damage Mode 1: Delamination starts at $2/3$ of the thickness at the center of the beam's length $25 \mu\text{s}$ after impact, see Figure 4 b). The single delamination propagates over the whole length of the beam resulting in two independent beams with rigid body movement forward in the direction of the impact combined with a free beam vibration response, see Figure 4 c) and d). This failure mode is found consistently in beams subjected to impacts energies in the range $240 \text{ J} - 340 \text{ J}$.

Figure 4: Beam response sequence under Damage Mode 1. $K_{e0} = 260 \text{ J}$.

Damage Mode 2: The specimen absorbs the impact resulting in a rigid body movement forward in the direction of the impact combined with a free beam vibration. As a result of the deformed shape induced by the vibration mode, fiber fracture under longitudinal compression occurs either at the impact side or backface layers, see Figure 5 b) and c), followed by delamination right under the fractured layer, approximately at $1/10$ of the thickness, see Figure 5 c). Afterwards, the free body vibration of the beam facilitates the propagation of the single exterior delamination, see figure 6 c). The initiation of the fracture at the impact side or backface layer occurs stochastically and it is the author's postulate that it is related to local non-homogeneities of the laminate interfaces. This failure mode is found consistently in beams subjected to impacts in the range $[350 - 400 \text{ J}]$.

Figure 5: Beam response sequence under Damage Mode 2. $K_{e0} = 370 \text{ J}$.

Damage Mode 3: Delamination starts at $2/3$ of the thickness at the center of the beam's length $25 \mu\text{s}$ after impact as in delamination mode 1, see Figure 6 b). $25 \mu\text{s}$ after, a second delamination appears

at about 1/4 of the thickness and appears to start at the edge of the impactor instead of at the center of the beam's length. These two delaminations propagate over the whole length of the beam resulting in three independent beams with rigid body movement forward in the direction of the impact combined with a free beam vibration response. This failure mode is found consistently in beams subjected to impacts in the range [400 – 500] J.

Figure 6: Beam response sequence under Damage Mode 3. $K_{e0} = 500$ J.

Over 500 J and up to 700 J, the damage sequence of events is coherent with Damage Mode 3 but with an increasing number of major delaminations throughout the thickness of the beam. The higher the impact energy the higher the number of delaminations. A common observation between all damage modes that exhibit major delaminations (Damage Modes 1, 3 and above) is that the first delamination starts 25 μ s after impact and is located at 3/4 of the thickness at the center of the beam's length. Figure 7 shows the final state of delaminations for 4 beams subjected to impact energies ranging from 600 J to 700 J.

Figure 7: Fully propagated delaminations in beams subjected to impacts over 500 J.

3.2 Backface Deformation

As can be seen in Figures 2-7, circular markers, $\phi = 2$ mm, spaced by 10 mm were drawn on the backface of the beams to be tracked. These measurements can be used as a correlation reference for numerical models as well as for comparing between different material configurations. Figure 8 b) and

c) show the captured back face displacement, u_x , for two sets of specimens tested under practically identical impact energies.

Figure 8: Backface displacement profile for two sets of specimens, plotted at 4 different time steps: $t = 20 \mu\text{s}$, $t = 50 \mu\text{s}$, $t = 100 \mu\text{s}$ and $t = 250 \mu\text{s}$ after impact.

4 DISCUSSION

Prior to the experimental campaign, it could be fairly anticipated that beams subjected to higher energy impacts will undergo higher number and more severe delaminations. However, for the energy impact range [350 - 400] J, a completely different damage mode arises. To the author's understanding, this hints to a difference in strain rate dependency of the interlaminar properties and the intralaminar properties.

Regarding the location of the first delamination onset, it has been found to be consistent at $\frac{3}{4}$ of the thickness and $25 \mu\text{s}$ after impact. The time resolution of $5 \mu\text{s}$ does not allow for a more precise determination within the range 20-30 μs . It is the author's intention to increase the sample population with higher frame rates in order to confirm or refute the consistency of the $25 \mu\text{s}$ measurement. The determination of the time origin, $t = 0$, also adds to the uncertainty of the delamination onset time. As the HS camera captures images every $5 \mu\text{s}$, the exact frame of the impact is impossible to determine because it is an instantaneous event. The experimentalist is then confronted with a frame where the impact has not yet taken place while in the immediate following frame the impactor and the beam have already come into contact. Hence, the determination of the time origin has also an uncertainty of $5 \mu\text{s}$. The consistent criterion followed during this study was to select as $t = 0$ the frame right before the impactor and the beam had started to come into contact.

4 CONCLUSION

An experimental setup has been presented that allows for the observation of the real-time damage propagation through the thickness of composite laminates. Observations in woven E-Glass/polyester specimens show delaminations initiating $25 \mu\text{s}$ after impact, located at $\frac{3}{4}$ of the thickness for impact energies in the range [240 - 350] U [400 - 700] J. Within the energy range [350 - 400] J a different damage mode stochastically appears at the outermost layer sets. The extraction of the back face displacement shows a very good repeatability of the experiment results. It is the author's intention to expand the sample population with higher frame rate measurements in order to enhance the determination of the delamination onset time.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. S. Langdon, W. J. Cantwell, Z. W. Guan, and G. N. Nurick, "The response of polymeric composite structures to air-blast loading: a state-of-the-art FULL CRITICAL REVIEW The response of polymeric composite structures to air-blast loading: a state-of-the-art," *Int. Mater. Rev.*, 2014.
- [2] B. P. Russell, T. Liu, N. A. Fleck, and V. S. Deshpande, "The soft impact of composite sandwich beams with a square-honeycomb core," *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 2012.
- [3] K. Karthikeyan, B. P. Russell, N. A. Fleck, M. O'masta, H. N. G. Wadley, and V. S. Deshpande, "The soft impact response of composite laminate beams," *Int. J. Impact Eng.*, 2013.